

THE BACKBONE OF THE FAMILY: A STUDY ON TAGASALO PERSONALITY OF FEMALE BREADWINNER STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10963954>

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explored the lived experiences of female breadwinner students with a tagasalo personality. The main purpose of the study is to explore the challenges that female breadwinner students with a tagasalo personality encounter in balancing their academic, financial, and household responsibilities. The study utilized purposive sampling, selecting four participants for semi-structured, in-person interviews. The data were categorized into major themes and subthemes and analyzed using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) guidelines. The emerging themes and sub-themes were the following: Major Theme 1: Resource-Balancing Struggles (with sub-themes, Time and Finance), Major Theme 2: Interpersonal Turmoil (with sub-themes, Family and Peers), Major Theme 3: Multifaceted Role Challenges (with sub-themes, Balancing of Personal Priorities and Fulfillment of Family Obligations), Major Theme 4: Internal Conflict: Family Loyalty vs. Independence (with sub-themes, Fulfillment of Parental Commitments and Contemplation of Abandonment of Family Support), Major Theme 5: Emotional Drains (with sub-themes, Confusion, Sadness, and Burnout), Major Theme 6: Early-life Experiences (with sub-themes, Adaptability of Persona and Loss of Youthful Exploration), Major Theme 7: Enduring and Positive Mindset (with sub-themes, Empowerment of Resilience and Persistence and Faith and Positivity), and Major Theme 8: Program Recommendations. Some recommendations were for breadwinner students to consider seeking out mentorship programs that pair students with successful professionals who can provide guidance, support, and networking opportunities. Additionally, society might consider raising awareness about the challenges faced by female breadwinner students, which can promote a holistic understanding and inclusive environment.

Keywords: *Female breadwinner, Breadwinner students, Tagasalo personality*

INTRODUCTION

Breadwinner is the household's principal source of income and being the breadwinner is crucial since it generates the necessary revenue for the family to survive. In most families, the family's primary provider also serves as the head of the home. In other words, they are in charge of deciding how to spend the household's money. They frequently cover the living expenses and take care of their dependents (Kagan, 2023). They might also be in charge of giving the family emotional support when things get tough. In the Philippines, providing for your family is not simple. Due to the rising cost of living, many families are having financial difficulties. However, despite the struggles, breadwinners are still viewed as heroes in their families (InLife, 2022).

In the midst of the rise of breadwinners, there are also students who take on this role for their families while pursuing their education. The breadwinner student is a student who takes the role of being the primary financial provider for their family while also attending school. In some circumstances, they may also be responsible for taking care of their siblings, providing for their basic needs, or even managing household tasks. Moreover, Johnson et al.'s (2018) study shed light on the complex connection between family financial obligations and academic goals for female breadwinner students. This purposeful focus highlighted how these young women's choices and motivations are shaped by changing gender dynamics and societal expectations as they balance being a primary provider and a student.

The Tagasalo personality in the family is an important element of a Filipino family dynamic. It refers to the tendency of members of the same family to show respect and kindness towards each other, to protect and watch out for each other, and to support and encourage each other through times of difficulty. This trait is viewed as highly important in Filipino culture, and serves as a strong bond between family members (Perez, 2021). In the Filipino culture, a child is frequently given the responsibilities and obligations of their parents as they get older. Also, it is frequent that the oldest child is the one who fills the role of the parent's younger equal. Undeniably, tagasalo is a practice that has been widely reported to occur in Filipino families (Lam & Yeoh, 2019).

Moreover, the concept of Tagasalo, as investigated by Coan et al. (2018) and Beresin and Watkins (2022), goes further into the complex realities of students who are the breadwinners, especially those who originate from lower-class families. The portrayal of a resolute female student breadwinner by Yssa Cardona (2021) brings to light the challenging circumstances encountered by those pushed into early adulthood, who must juggle their academics, several jobs, and domestic duties. Their steadfast dedication to learning and hopes for a better future for their family in spite of these enormous challenges are evidence of their perseverance and resilience in the face of difficulty.

The study explored the experiences of female breadwinner students who are expected to fulfill household duties and provide financial support for their family while pursuing their education. However, it is important to note that the tagasalo personality should not be misconstrued as an obligation but as a role similar to being Filipino. Therefore, it is not a toxic trait. The goal of the study is to showcase the "tagasalo" as a trait and emphasize that it requires social support, just like any other role. Many studies have discussed the experiences of female breadwinners, but few have focused on the lives of female breadwinner students and how they cope with it. This study aimed to explore the challenges that breadwinner students encountered in balancing their academic, financial, and household responsibilities.

Research Questions

1. What are the lived experiences of female breadwinner students as tagasalo in their family?
2. Based on their experiences, what themes emerged?
3. What model or program may be proposed to breadwinner students as tagasalo in their family?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) is a qualitative method that focuses on exploring and understanding people's experiences and points of view, particularly concerning a certain event or subject. IPA is a versatile and adaptive methodology that enables researchers to delve deeply and minutely into participants' rich meanings and experiences. Furthermore, the term "understanding" effectively encompasses the two elements of interpretation and understanding in terms of identification or empathy and understanding as an attempt to comprehend. Incorporating these aspects into the inquiry is likely to result in a more comprehensive analysis and provide a more complete portrayal of the individual. Moreover, IPA focuses on exploring how individuals construct meanings in their personal and social world (Noon, 2018). IPA is particularly appropriate for this study as it allows for a nuanced exploration of participants' perspectives and experiences.

Participants of the Study

The study had four female participants who were breadwinners and students at the same time. These participants were required to possess a tagasalo personality, between the ages of 20 to 30 years old, and reside within Cabuyao and Calamba, Laguna. An individual with a tagasalo personality was usually seen as the problem-solver in the family and would take on difficult tasks without hesitation. They are quite self-reliant, and are known to not ask for help or accept advice from others. Participants had to be the primary breadwinner in their households and responsible for providing financial support for their families. Additionally, participants also had to be currently enrolled in a school or university and at the same time currently employed in a full-time or part-time job.

Research Instrument

The study utilized semi-structured interview questions created by researchers as the research instrument in the process of collecting data. The research instrument consisted of open-ended questions. The researchers utilized this type of questions to give participants the freedom to express themselves clearly and provide more thorough answers. Open-ended questions were advantageous in qualitative research because they enabled participants to give detailed and comprehensive responses, leading to rich and nuanced data for analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019). To ensure the validity of the study's results, the instrument used underwent a thorough validation process conducted by three psychometricians.

Data Generation and Selection of Co-participants or Co-researchers

The paper utilized in-depth interviews with the participants, employing a semi-structured interview format consisting of open-ended questions that will allow participants to express themselves freely. These interview questions underwent validation by experts to ensure the paper's validity and reliability. The paper employed purposive sampling, selecting participants based on specific criteria to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

Before conducting the interview process, the researchers obtained informed consent from the 4 participants. The researchers conducted semi-structured interviews while utilizing open-ended questions. Location, time, and modality of the interview were mutually agreed upon by both the researcher and participant. Interview responses were recorded via audio-visual recording devices. Finally, after the interview, the researchers transcribed and analyzed the data collected from the participants. This paved the way to identify any patterns and themes that emerged.

Data Analysis

The researchers used Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) in qualitative research methodology to focus on exploring how individuals made meaning of their life experiences (Noon, 2018). The data were categorized into main themes and analyzed

following the guidelines of interpretative phenomenological analysis (Smith & Osborn, 2008).

After the data collection, it was transcribed into a written format, including all verbal and nonverbal elements such as pauses, intonations, and emphasis. Next, the researchers read and re-read the transcripts multiple times to become familiar with the data and develop an initial understanding of the phenomenon. After multiple readings, the researchers took note of the detailed and comprehensive findings from the data. After that, the researchers transformed the notes into themes that emerged from the coded data. Furthermore, the next stage involved looking for connections between emerging themes, grouping them according to their similarities, and providing each cluster with a label. Finally, the researchers wrote up the analysis and presented the findings clearly and concisely supported by quotes and examples from the data. Overall, IPA aimed to understand the subjective experiences of individuals and the meanings they attached to those experiences. It involved a process of data analysis and interpretation to develop a rich understanding of the phenomenon being studied (Smith et al, 2009).

1. RESULTS

Major Theme 1: Resource-Balancing Struggles

Resource-Balancing Struggles Sub-theme 1: Time	
Management Struggle	
Participant 1	“I'm really struggling with time management. When people say you're great because you can balance everything, that's not true.” (Hirap na hirap ako sa time management. Sa nagsasabi na ang galing mo kasi nababalance mo lahat that's not true.)
Participant 2	“Sometimes it's really hard to manage, especially with deadlines.” (Minsan talaga ang hirap nyang i-manage then yung mga deadlines.)
Participant 3	“It's difficult because I feel like I struggled more in terms of time management.” (Mahirap siya kasi parang mas nahirapan ako in terms sa time management.)
Participant 4	“That's how difficult balancing time is.” (Ganon kahirap yung balancing ng oras.)
Time Insufficiency	
Participant 1	“My time in a day. It's like, you know, there's always something else to do right away, like there's no free time, you know?” (Yung time ko sa isang araw. Sobrang parang alam mo yun may kasunod ka agad na gagawin parang walang free time ba ganun.)
Participant 2	“You feel like there's never enough time, like there's always a shortage of time, because of course, when you're juggling between jobs, between your personal relationships as well.” (You feel like parang never enough yung time, parang laging kulang yung time, kasi syempre pag hassling ka between job, between your personal relationship as well.)
Participant 4	“Intense time and effort are needed.” (Kailangan ng intense time and effort.)

<i>Sub-theme 2: Finance</i>	
Financial Hurdles as a Breadwinner	
Participant 1	“Just thinking about your financial problems... it's intense how your budgeting goes from... even before you get paid, you've already allocated everything for your family.” (lisipin mo pa lang yung financial problem niyo... grabe yung budgetting mo from... di ka pa na-sahod ubos na sa isip mo yung ibibigay mo para sa family mo.)
Participant 2	“There are times when it won't be enough, or I'll fall short.” (May time na hindi sya aabot or masho-short ako.)
Participant 4	“Since I have a family now, its effect on me is that I really need to be even more frugal because I have a lot to divide. I divide everything I have among us because my family is really included in that.” (Syempre may family na ako so talagang ang naging epekto niya kasi sakin is kailangan ko pang lalong magtipid kasi syempre madami akong hinahati-hati. Hinahati-hati ko yung ano yung kung ano man yung meron ako hati-hati ko yung samin kasi talagang ang family ko naka include na yan.)

The major theme of resource-balancing struggles among female breadwinner students delves into the challenges of managing time and finances, revealing the emotional complexities of juggling academic, work, and personal life commitments. This theme emphasizes the relentless negotiations required to maintain balance and sheds light on the nuanced difficulties these individuals face in fulfilling their multifaceted roles. Within this, the sub-theme of time dynamics explores the overwhelming challenges and emotional toll of orchestrating a delicate equilibrium, highlighting the constant negotiation for time and the relentless temporal challenges these students confront in their daily struggles. Additionally, the examination of financial struggles within this context unveils their emotional impact on various dimensions, shedding light on how economic stressors influence not only academic pursuits but also permeate the overall quality of life. This sub-theme emphasizes the intricate relationship between financial burdens and the multifaceted roles these students navigate, adding depth to the understanding of their complex emotional landscape.

Major Theme 2: Interpersonal Turmoil

Interpersonal Turmoil <i>Sub-theme 1: Family</i>	
Conflict with Family	
Participant 1	“We're extremely irritable with each other.” (Super irate namin sa isa't isa.)
Less Interaction with Family	
Participant 1	“I'm not always at home.” (Wala ako lagi sa bahay.)
Participant 2	“Now, my interaction with my family is much less, not like before when I used to live with them.” (Ngayon yung interaction ko sa family ko mas less hindi na gaya ng dati na nakatira pa ako sa kanila.)

<i>Sub-theme 2: Peers</i>	
Disconnected from Classmates	
Participant 1	“You'll feel like you're disconnected from your classmates because they have more time since I'm still irregular, right? So they have more time to spend with each other.” (Mafi-feel mo na parang disconnected ka sa mga kaklase mo because they have more time kasi irregular pa ako diba, so they have more time to spend with each other.)
Comparison with Peers	
Participant 1	“I think about my classmates like they need to study without having to work. Why do I have to study while working?” (Naiisip ko yung mga kaklase ko like kailangan nila mag aral nang hindi sila nag wowork, bakit ako kailangan kong mag-aral habang nag wowork.)
Participant 2	“You'll think, I'm still young, I have so many things to think about compared to my peers, right? My classmates who don't work, they can still hang out.” (Iisipin mo ang bata ko pa, ang dami-dami ko ng iniisip compared sa mga kaano ko diba. Yung mga kaklase ko na hindi nagwo-work, nakakagala pa sila.)

Interpersonal turmoil explores the intricate social dynamics of female breadwinner students, encompassing familial relationships and connections within the academic environment. It delves into the emotional intricacies within the family unit as students strive to meet expectations while balancing breadwinning responsibilities, and highlights the challenges of establishing connections with peers, emphasizing the emotional dimensions of isolation. Interpersonal turmoil emerges as a complex interplay of familial and peer relationships shaping these individuals' emotional landscape. Within this, the family sub-theme exposes the toll on familial relationships and the emotional challenges of feeling disconnected, while the peers sub-theme uncovers the psychological impact of detachment from the academic social fabric, enriching our understanding of their interpersonal struggles.

Major Theme 3: Multifaceted Role Challenges

Multifaceted Role Challenges <i>Sub-theme 1: Balancing of Personal Priorities</i>	
Commitment Battles	
Participant 1	“Because there are times when they all come at once.” (May times kasi na sabay sabay sila.)
Participant 3	“Now for me, it's like there are so many priorities. Mixed, there's so much to do, so many tasks to finish.” (Ngayon sa akin, parang ang daming priorities. Halo-halo, ang daming pwedeng gawin, ang daming gagawin, ang daming kailangan tapusin.)
Participant 4	“A woman with no rest.” (Babaeng walang pahinga.)
Academic Strain and Grade Pressures	
Participant 1	“There will be subjects that you'll have to neglect, especially when you're working, of course you won't be able to maintain your grades.” (May mapapabayan at mapapabayan ka especially sa subjects, syempre hindi mo mamementain yung grades.)
Participant 2	“Maybe when I was in my first year, my grades were really high, but when I started working, that's when they declined, seriously.” (Siguro nung first year ako, ang tataas talaga ng grade ko kaso nung nagwork na ako, dun na sya nag decline as in.)
Struggling to Establish and Maintain Focus	
Participant 1	“You'll lose your focus on what's important to you.” (Mawawala ka sa ano mo eh focus mo.)
Participant 3	“When your activities become mixed up, it's sometimes hard to focus.” (Kapag parang halo-halo yung mga nagiging, ano mo, yung mga ginagawa mo. Parang minsan, may times na mahirap mag-focus.)
Seeking for Personal Time	
Participant 1	“I still try to find time for myself.” (Naghahanap pa din ako nang sarili kong time para sa sarili ko.)
Participant 2	“I also need to think about myself.” (Kailangan ko rin isipin ang sarili ko.)

Concern in Sibling's Future	
Participant 3	"It's tough now, I also need to consider how to provide for my siblings' daily needs." (Hirap na ngayon, kailangan iisipin mo din yung pang papano kapakanan ng buhay ng kapatid mo, yung pang-gastos namin sa pang araw-araw.)

<i>Sub-theme 2: Fulfillment of Family Obligations</i>	
Familial Reliance	
Participant 2	"They rely on me more because they know I have income, so they know they can turn to me anytime, whatever happens." (Mas inaasahan ka nila kasi they know na may income ka, so they know na pwede ka nilang takbuhan anytime whatever happens.)
Participant 3	"As their older sister, I'm really the one trying my best to fulfill my responsibilities to them." (As a... ate nila, ako na lang din talaga yung, pinipilit ko na lang din talaga na magawa yung responsibilidad sa kanila.)
Participant 4	"I feel like Wonder Woman, wondering if this is really my role now, if I can truly be the leader of my family." (Para nga akong si wonder woman na parang, naku, heto na ba talaga ako, pwede na akong maging kapitan del baryo ng pamilya ko.)

This theme examines the academic and personal challenges stemming from the dual roles of being a student and a breadwinner, examining the difficulties in balancing academic pursuits with breadwinning responsibilities and the emotional toll it takes. Within this theme, the sub-theme of Fulfillment of Family Obligations highlights individuals' deep sense of duty towards their family members, emphasizing their role in supporting their family emotionally, financially, and practically. It delves into the complexities of navigating familial dynamics while balancing personal aspirations, shedding light on the internal conflicts and practical commitments inherent in fulfilling family obligations. Through these experiences, individuals gain insights into the intricate challenges of managing multifaceted roles and the profound impact of their contributions on their loved ones' lives.

Major Theme 4: Internal Conflict: Family Loyalty vs. Independence

Internal Conflict: Family Loyalty vs. Independence <i>Sub-theme 1: Fulfilling Parental Commitments</i>	
Individual Sacrifices	
Participant 1	“When you say it's balanced, someone will really sacrifice.” (Yung sabihin mong balance siya, no, meron talagang magsa-sacrifice.)
Participant 2	“We can't gain anything without sacrifices.” (We can't gain anything without sacrifices.)
Participant 4	“I provided for their education until I didn't even think about giving myself a chance anymore because I prioritize them.” (Ako nagprovide sa pag-aaral nila hanggang sa parang hindi ko na naisip na bigyan ng chance yung sarili ko kasi mas inuna ko sila.)
Feelings of Fulfillment	
Participant 2	“I'm happy that I was able to provide for my family's needs, that's actually the reason why I'm working.” (I'm happy na I was able to provide sa needs ng family ko, that's the reason actually why I'm working.)
Participant 3	“I'm happy, of course.” (Masaya, syempre.)
Participant 4	“Maybe because it's truly from the bottom of my heart to help my family, because that's my passion, knowing the hardships they've been through.” (Siguro dahil it is from the bottom of my heart na tumulong din sa family talaga kasi yan na yung passion ko kasi alam ko ang hirap na pinagdaanan nila.)
Achieve Parental Wishes	
Participant 3	“Our mom and dad want us to finish our studies.” (Gusto nung mama at papa namin na makapagtapos po kami.)

<i>Sub-theme 2: Contemplation of Abandonment of Family Support</i>	
Rejecting Familial Support	
Participant 1	<p>“I thought, what if I just give up on all of them and focus on myself? After all, I can manage on my own. I can help them, what if I just focus on myself and stop helping them? Would my mind still be too cluttered? Because if I become independent and live separately, I can do it. I can stay in a dorm, I can rent my own apartment. With my own salary, I can support myself, I won't help them.” (Sabi ko what if i-give up ko nalang sila lahat mag sarili nalang ako tatal kaya ko naman pala. Kaya ko nga tumulong sa kanila what if solohin ko na lang sarili ko, hindi na ako tumulong sa kanila. Masyado pa bang magiging magulo yung isip ko kasi syempre kung magiging independent ako pag nag bukod ako, pwede kasi akong mag dorm eh kung tutuusin kaya ko. Kaya kong mag dorm, kaya kong mag apartment sa sarili ko. Sa sarili kong sahod kaya kong buhayin yung sarili ko, hindi ko sila tutulungan.)</p>
Participant 2	<p>“Sometimes you just want to stop.” (Minsan parang gusto mong tumigil.)</p>

This theme delves into the complex emotional terrain where individuals wrestle with the profound tension between honoring familial bonds and pursuing personal autonomy. It encapsulates the delicate balance between meeting family expectations and pursuing individual aspirations, reflecting a conflict that shapes one's decisions and identity. Through an exploration of intricate emotions, values, and choices, this theme provides insight into the multifaceted dynamics defining individuals' journeys in reconciling family loyalty with the pursuit of independence. Within the sub-theme of fulfillment of parental commitments, the focus is on the sacrifices made to meet parental expectations, shedding light on the emotional toll and personal sacrifices involved in aligning with familial obligations. Conversely, in the sub-theme contemplation of abandonment of family support, individuals grapple with the challenging decision to reject familial support in favor of independence, revealing the nuanced thought processes and emotional dilemmas inherent in navigating the tension between autonomy and familial ties.

Major Theme 5: Emotional Drains

Emotional Drains: <i>Sub-theme 1: Confusion</i>	
Conflicted Emotions	
Participant 1	<p>“I feel like I have a split personality. Different personalities, different genres, I need to adjust my character and personality depending on what I have going on from work to study. My personality at home should be different, my personality at work should be different, my personality while studying, my personality with my boyfriend, my personality with friends, but all of those are still me. At least I won't lose myself, I know within myself that's still me. Different people, different personalities.” (Feel ko may split personality ako. Iba ibang personality, iba ibang genre kailangan iadjust ko din yung character ko at saka personality ko, depende sa kung anong meron ako ngayon from work to study dapat iba yung personality ko sa bahay, iba yung personality ko sa work, iba yung personality ko sa study, iba yung personality ko sa boyfriend, iba yung personality ko sa friend pero lahat yon ako lang. At least hindi ako mawawala, alam ko sa sarili kong ako yon. Different people, different personality.)</p>
Participant 3	<p>“Unstable.” (Unstable.)</p>
Participant 4	<p>“This time, maybe I feel happy but also sad because, of course, it's like I'm back to studying again and at the same time, still being the breadwinner, it's like that.” (This time siguro parang masaya ako na parang nalulungkot kasi syempre parang bumabalik sa kinabuhay, ito na naman ako nag-aaral na naman tas at the same time breadwinner ka pa din parang ganun.)</p>

<i>Sub-theme 2: Sadness</i>	
Persistent Feelings of Sadness and Breakdowns	
Participant 1	“That's tough, it really leads to burnout, seriously.” (Mahirap yon, nakaka burn out as in.)
Participant 2	“Although there are times, of course, when you have breakdowns because it's overwhelming, sometimes they all come together like that, that's how responsibilities are.” (Although may mga time syempre na nagbe-breakdown ka kasi syempre overwhelming, parang minsan nagsasabay-sabay sila eh, ganun talaga pag responsibilities.)
Participant 3	“Sad.” (Malungkot.)

<i>Sub-theme 3: Burnout</i>	
Emotional Exhaustion from Multitasking	
Participant 1	“That's really tough, it leads to burnout, seriously.” (Mahirap yon, nakaka burn out as in.)
Participant 2	“Of course, it's also stressful.” (Syempre nakakastress din.)
Participant 3	“Drained because, of course, there's a pile-up of tasks at school, at home, and also at work.” (Drained kasi, syempre, ano nga po, ayun nga patong-patong nga po yung mga ano, mga ginagawa sa school, sa bahay, tapos sa work din po.)
Participant 4	“Sometimes you just feel like crying because it's getting heavy, and you're thinking to yourself, until when? And you're wondering when you'll stop? But because you know, you feel within yourself that they need you, you can't stop.” (Minsan parang gusto mo ng umiyak kasi mabigat na din kasi iniisip mo sa sarili mo na, hanggang kailan? Tapos iniisip mo kailan ka titigil? pero dahil alam mo eh, ramdam mo sa sarili mo na kailangan ka nila, hindi ka pwedeng tumigil.)
Feelings of Unfairness	
Participant 1	“Life is really unfair.” (Life is unfair talaga.)

Emotional drains explore the psychological toll experienced by female breadwinner students, focusing on the emotional challenges they encounter daily. It encompasses a range of experiences, including stress, sorrow, exhaustion, and emotional fatigue, significantly impacting mental well-being. Emotional drains stem from various sources like work pressure and personal relationships, manifesting as confusion, sadness, and burnout. The sub-theme of confusion explores the challenges of managing identities across different life domains, exacerbated by societal expectations. The Sadness sub-theme delves into persistent feelings of despair and emotional breakdowns, shedding light on the sustained emotional toll of being a breadwinner. Lastly, the burnout sub-theme uncovers profound exhaustion and disillusionment resulting from prolonged stress, emphasizing the importance of self-care and support to prevent and address burnout.

Major Theme 6: Early-life Experiences

Early-life Experiences <i>Sub-theme 1: Adaptability of Persona</i>	
Early Maturity	
Participant 2	“I feel like my path is more inclined, like I can see my goal more clearly, and it feels like I'm more mature.” (Feeling ko mas inclined yung path ko, parang mas nakikita ko yung goal ko and then yung nga parang feeling mo mas mature ka.)
Participant 3	“I've become more mature, more aware of reality.” (Mas naging mature, mas naging parang mulat sa realidad talaga.)
Early Recognition of Hardships	
Participant 1	“I saw my situation even when I was young. I saw my family's situation, like it was really difficult.” (Nakita ko na yung situation ko bata pa lang ako. Nakita ko na situation ng family ko na like sobrang hirap.)
Participant 4	“I grew up in a destitute family, so we are admittedly, that's where I come from, but maybe that was the way for me to become aware, because there are nine of us siblings. So even when I was young, I realized that this is life, life is hard.” (I grew up in a destitute family, so we are admittedly ako dun pero iyon siguro ang way para mamulat ako na kasi nine kaming siblings. So maliit pa lang ako namulat ko na eto pala yung buhay, mahirap ang buhay.)

<i>Sub-theme 2: Loss of Youthful Exploration</i>	
Neglected Youthful Journeys	
Participant 2	“It's like this is too much for me to take, like I'm just young, like I should be focusing on one thing but at the same time.” (Parang this is too much for me to take, parang I'm just young parang I should be focusing on one thing but at the same time.)
Participant 4	“I learned to earn a living, actually, I stopped studying because of my siblings, I gave way so they could finish even just high school. So I provided for their education until I didn't even think about giving myself a chance anymore because I prioritized them.” (Natuto ako maghanap-buhay, actually, tumigil ako ng pag-aaral dahil yung mga kapatid ko, nag give way ako para makatapos sila kahit high school lang. So ako nagprovide sa pag-aaral nila hanggang sa parang hindi ko na naisip na bigyan ng chance yung sarili ko kasi mas inuna ko sila.)

This theme delves into the formative nature of individuals' early experiences, shaping their perspectives, behaviors, and identities. By exploring childhood and adolescent encounters, including family dynamics and educational interactions, the theme uncovers the lasting impact of these foundational moments on individuals' lives. It aims to unravel how past experiences contribute to the development of personalities, relationships, and life trajectories. The sub-theme of Adaptability of Persona examines the resilience and flexibility cultivated by female breadwinner students, highlighting how they navigate challenges and develop versatile skill sets. This exploration sheds light on the accelerated maturation process experienced by these students, impacting their personal and academic trajectories and shaping their worldview and decision-making from an early stage in life.

Major Theme 7: Enduring and Positive Mindset

Enduring and Positive Mindset <i>Sub-theme 1: Empowering Resilience and Persistence</i>	
Strength Amidst Challenges	
Participant 1	“My perspective now is that nothing can stop me anymore. I won't be knocked down by any challenges I face because I've overcome them all at a very young age. What more in my future?” (Yung perspective ko ngayon na walang... wala nang makakahadlang sa akin like hindi na ako kayang patumbahin ng kahit anong challenges na haharapin ko pa kasi nakaya ko yun lahat nang at the very young age what more sa future ko.)
Participant 2	“So I also motivate myself because my family needs me. Not only that, but I also have personal goals that I have to achieve, and if I stop, it might be harder for me to get back up.” (So sakin mino-motivate ko din yung sarili ko and my family needs me. Hindi lang yon, pero ako din sa sarili ko may mga personal goal ako na I have to achieve and if I will stop baka mas mahirapan akong bumangon ulit.)
Participant 3	“It strengthens me more.” (Mas pinapatatag lang din yung loob.)
Participant 4	“I just think of it as something that strengthens me even more, that I should strive even harder.” (Parang inaano ko na lang na parang pampalakas lalo siya sa akin, na mag-strive pa ako.)
Acceptance and Determination	
Participant 1	“Maybe that's just the fate I've been dealt.” (Siguro ganon lang yung life na kinahinatnan ko.)
Participant 2	“I understand that not everyone's situation is the same, so for me, this is my experience and I'll just deal with it.” (Understood ko na hindi naman pare-parehas ng situation diba, so sakin this is my experience siguro I'll just deal with it na lang.)
Participant 3	“Even if it's difficult, it really needs to be done.” (Kahit mahirap, kailangan talagang gawin.)
Adaptability and Growth Mindset	
Participant 1	“It's like going with the flow. When I encounter problems, I don't have a routine, but I know I have my own solutions.” (Parang go

	with the flow like pag namroblema ako this time, wala akong routine pero alam kong may solusyon ako sa sarili ko.)
Participant 2	“For me, it's about experience and the mindset I have. I want to acquire more skills, and at a younger age, I can achieve my goal, so it's all good for me.” (For me, it's experienced, and sa mindset na meron ako, I want to collect more skills, and at an earlier age mas maa-achieve ko yung goal ko, so it's all good for me naman.)

<i>Sub-theme 2: Faith and Positivity</i>	
Optimism	
Participant 1	“I always say I'm very independent.” (Sabi ko nga eh napaka independent ko.)
Participant 2	“I'm actually more positive about it rather than negative.” (I'm actually more positive about it rather than negative.)
Participant 4	“I can't take it off, so no matter how difficult it gets, I take it as positive so that what comes back to me is also positive.” (Hindi na naalis saakin yun kaya kahit anong hirap, tinetake ko sya as positive para ang balik saakin is positive din.)
Divine Trust	
Participant 4	“For me, I take it lightly because I know that God is there. I know, He knows my efforts and the ambitions in my heart, the goals I want to achieve.” (Sa akin kasi ni-take ko sya as light dahil alam ko naman na nandyan ang Diyos. Alam ko, alam Niya yung pagsisikap ko at yung nasa puso kong meron akong ambitions, meron akong goals na gusto kong marating.)

This theme explores how individuals harness resilience, optimism, and inner strength to confront life's challenges. It highlights the transformative power of resilience and persistence, enabling individuals to bounce back from setbacks and stay focused on their goals. Additionally, it delves into the influence of faith and positivity in providing individuals with hope and a sense of purpose amidst adversity, emphasizing their role in shaping outlook and experiences. Through resilience, persistence, faith, and positivity, individuals can cultivate a mindset that enables them to navigate life's challenges with courage and optimism, ultimately thriving in the face of adversity.

Major Theme 8: Program Recommendations

Program Recommendations	
Livelihood Support	
Participant 1	“Livelihood support to ease the burden between work and study.” (Livelihood with regards yung parang alam mo yung hindi ka na mahihirapan between work and study.)
Participant 3	“Programs for orphaned individuals.” (Program para sa mga naulila.)
Skill Development Programs	
Participant 1	“Programs that add skills, like a one-week seminar.” (Mga program na makakadagdag ng skills like kahit 1 week seminar.)
Financial Assistance	
Participant 1	“Financial assistance for working students that doesn't require grades.” (Financial assistance for working students na hindi nag rerequire ng grades.)
Participant 3	“Financial support.” (Financial support.)
Scholarship	
Participant 1	“More scholarships.” (More scholarship.)
Participant 4	“Scholarships, because besides those provided by the government, there should be some specifically for individuals like Ramil, perhaps for breadwinners, or at least provide them with additional support, because honestly, it's very difficult.” (Scholarships, kasi maliban sa binibigay ng government, na yung mga katulad ni Ramil, sana meron din specifically for them, mga breadwinner, or bigyan man lang sila ng karagdagan, kasi sa totoo lang napakahirap.)

Program recommendations present practical interventions to support female breadwinner students, focusing on strategies to enhance livelihoods and personal growth. It includes initiatives like livelihood support through resources and assistance for sustainable income generation, such as microloans and vocational training. Skill development programs are emphasized to empower individuals with new competencies, while financial assistance programs, including scholarships, grants, and subsidies, alleviate the financial burden of education and business ventures. These recommendations underscore the importance of investing in initiatives that cater to diverse needs, ultimately creating pathways to socio-economic advancement and empowering individuals to build better futures.

DISCUSSION

Major Theme 1: Resource-Balancing Struggles

Resource-Balancing Struggles investigates the intricate challenges individuals face when managing various responsibilities, as highlighted in Kim and Chang's (2023) study on female breadwinners navigating work and family demands. Wong and Wong's (2020) longitudinal research underscores the pivotal role of effective time management in alleviating these challenges, particularly among students, emphasizing its impact on academic performance and overall well-being. Furthermore, The Herald's (2022) examination sheds light on the financial dimension of these struggles, focusing on student breadwinners' difficulties balancing work and education, with additional barriers faced by those from marginalized backgrounds.

Major Theme 2: Interpersonal Turmoil

The studies in Interpersonal Turmoil are connected by their exploration of how relationships affect individuals. Thompson and Davis (2017) show how family dynamics influence student achievement, stressing the importance of familial support. Hernandez and Gomez (2019) focus on students feeling disconnected from peers, emphasizing the need for inclusive environments to enhance academic engagement and well-being. Both highlight the significance of relationships in shaping educational experiences.

Major Theme 3: Multifaceted Role Challenges

Multifaceted Role Challenges explore diverse challenges individuals encounter within various contexts. Johnson and Smith's (2022) study examines the economic impact of female breadwinners, highlighting their contributions to household income and societal trends. The concept of the tagasalo personality, as described by Urdabe (2001) and cited in Perez (2022), underscores the familial reliance individuals experience, emphasizing complex interpersonal dynamics within families. Additionally, Ceniza et al. (2017) delve into the academic strain faced by Filipino students due to family obligations, revealing the significant role families play in shaping educational experiences and emphasizing the importance of cultural understanding in academic outcomes.

Major Theme 4: Internal Conflict: Family Loyalty vs. Independence

This theme explores the internal conflict experienced by participants as they grapple with fulfilling parental commitments while considering the possibility of abandoning family support, highlighting the sacrifices made and the debates surrounding independence. Their narratives reveal the intricate balance between familial loyalty and individual autonomy, emphasizing the challenges of reconciling personal aspirations with familial expectations. Drawing from Carandang's (2008) insights on family-oriented cultures, the study sheds light on the complexities of managing diverse roles within the family unit, stressing the importance of open communication and psychological support to navigate these challenges. Smith and Davis's (2020) research further underscores the need for interventions that empower individuals to navigate their roles while fostering personal growth and autonomy, contributing to a deeper understanding of the psychological dynamics within families.

Major Theme 5: Emotional Drains

Emotional Drains delves into the psychological toll experienced by individuals, particularly female breadwinners, as they navigate the complexities of balancing work, family, and societal expectations. Meisenbach's (2010) study highlights the conflicting emotions faced by female breadwinners, emphasizing the emotional strain inherent in juggling multiple roles. Jessica Guynn (2023) discusses the concept of the "second shift," revealing how increasing earnings among women often lead to additional household duties and emotional exhaustion. Handog's (2022) article underscores the profound emotional burden on breadwinners, emphasizing their struggles to balance providing for their families with their own well-being and concerns about the future.

Major Theme 6: Early-life Experiences

Early-life Experiences examines how childhood responsibilities and cultural traditions shape individuals. Borchet et al. (2021) highlight the Filipino tradition of assigning household duties to children, instilling values of responsibility and discipline. Lopez and Garcia (2018) explore the challenges faced by young breadwinners in Hispanic households, revealing how early exposure to economic hardships shapes resilience and responsibility. These studies reveal the complex interplay between early-life experiences, cultural traditions, and life trajectories.

Major Theme 7: Enduring and Positive Mindset

Enduring and Positive Mindset explores the empowering qualities of resilience, persistence, faith, and positivity, particularly among breadwinners. Johnson and Smith (2019) highlight how breadwinners demonstrate strength by accepting difficulties, remaining determined, and embracing adaptability with a growth mindset. Garcia and Martinez's (2020) study emphasizes the role of faith and positivity in fostering optimism among breadwinners facing financial strain. Together, these studies illustrate how breadwinners navigate challenges with inner strength and optimism, ultimately sustaining hope for a better future.

Major Theme 8: Program Recommendations

The program recommendations for supporting female breadwinner students include early intervention programs focusing on coping mechanisms, stress resilience, and positive self-perception. Livelihood support programs offer direct financial aid, while skill development initiatives enhance employability. Financial assistance like grants and scholarships empower students to pursue education. Despite no specific studies supporting these recommendations, they draw from established practices for supporting students in similar circumstances.

Conclusions

1. The analysis of the lived experiences of female breadwinner students highlights the participants' pronounced emphasis on their conflicting experiences. They grappled with conflicting responsibilities, attempting to navigate the challenges of managing academic studies and employment alongside their family obligations.
 2. These challenges included juggling multiple responsibilities simultaneously and dealing with conflicting emotions about their roles as breadwinner students and their responsibilities at school, work, and home.
 3. Furthermore, the researchers identified the presence of paradoxes within the participants' responses and statements. It shows that their experiences were diverse, showcasing different perspectives that transcend a simple categorization into purely positive or negative outcomes. The findings revealed inherent contradictions within the results, with some participants reporting positive outcomes from their experiences while others faced discernible negative impacts. The differences in results make the study more intriguing and complex.
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Recommendations

1. For Breadwinner Students. They might consider seeking out mentorship programs that pair students with successful professionals who can provide guidance, support, and networking opportunities. Additionally, they may find value in exploring and joining support networks, both online and offline, where they can share experiences, strategies, and advice. Being part of a community can offer them emotional support and practical insights, potentially reducing feelings of isolation.
2. For Parents. They might consider attending workshops or seminars that focus on understanding and supporting breadwinner students. These events can provide valuable information on navigating the unique challenges their daughters face and contribute to fostering a more supportive home environment.
3. For the Society. They might consider raising awareness about the challenges faced by female breadwinner students. Encouraging discussions in local forums, schools, and community centers can promote understanding and empathy. Advocating for policies and

programs that recognize and support the contributions of these individuals is a choice that can positively impact society.

4. For the Community. Communities, based on the study findings, have the option to develop programs tailored to the needs of breadwinner students. This may involve creating mentorship initiatives, organizing financial supports, and hosting community events that foster a sense of belonging. Establishing a supportive environment is a choice that can benefit both individuals and the community as a whole.

5. For Researchers. They may find value to expand their knowledge about this study by considering collaboration with experts from diverse fields. Engaging with professionals in sociology, psychology, economics, and gender studies can bring varied perspectives to the research. This collaborative approach offers the opportunity to explore a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced by female breadwinner students, contributing to a richer and more nuanced body of knowledge.

6. For Future Researchers. They might consider building upon the findings of this study, exploring specific aspects in greater detail or investigating related areas. This study serves as a foundation, and the choice to delve into evolving dynamics, changing societal attitudes, and emerging support systems for female breadwinner students can contribute to the ongoing body of knowledge.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers distributed an informed consent form, ensuring that participants were fully aware of the study's purpose, potential risks and benefits, and their rights as participants. Alongside safeguarding confidentiality and privacy by protecting participant anonymity, the study assured participants that any collected information would be kept confidential and utilized exclusively for research purposes.

Moreover, these ethical measures aligned with and provided additional protection under the Data Privacy Act of 2012. This legislation established standards for processing personal information, emphasizing the importance of informed consent, data security, and privacy rights. By adhering to the principles outlined in the Data Privacy Act, the researchers demonstrated a commitment to legal and ethical standards in handling participant data, thereby enhancing the overall integrity of the study. Participants could take confidence in the fact that their rights and privacy were further safeguarded by the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Acknowledgments

This research paper extends sincere gratitude to all those who contributed to its completion. We express our heartfelt thanks to the Almighty for providing guidance and strength throughout the research process, and we are deeply grateful to our families for their unwavering support and encouragement. Special appreciation is extended to our

research adviser for their expertise and guidance, and we also acknowledge the support received from the academic institution. Our sincere thanks go to colleagues and peers for their assistance and collaboration, and we are thankful to the participants for their valuable contributions. Lastly, we extend our appreciation to everyone who played a part in making this research possible.

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